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Additional data of ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from Euboea Island, Central Greece

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Abstract: A list of 78 ant species and morphospecies collected in June 2025 from 58 sites in the Euboea Island is presented. First nest samples with gynes of endemic *Temnothorax euboeae* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2022, and hitherto not described gynes of *Aphaenogaster tristis* BOROWIEC *et al.*, 2024 and *Temnothorax brackoi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2019 were collected. An updated list of 92 species and morphospecies known from the Euboea Island is given.

Key words: ants, Greece, faunistics.

INTRODUCTION

The ant fauna of Greece, with at least 320 confirmed species, is probably the richest in Europe, but studies on the ant biodiversity of this country remain incomplete, as the taxonomic status of more than 23 taxa still remains unresolved, and most of them are likely undescribed species (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2022, 2025; our unpublished data).

The first comprehensive checklist of Greek ants was compiled by LEGAKIS (2011). In the last 14 years, the ant fauna of Greece has been studied more intensively as part of the inventory of ants in the Mediterranean region (see references in BOROWIEC *et al.* 2024). The first two volumes of the monograph on Greek ants (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2022, 2025) will likely enable regional research through citizen science, as evidenced by the effects of such activity in other Mediterranean countries (ARCOS 2025, DEMETRIOU *et al.* 2025).

Euboea or Evia (Greek: Εύβοια or Εβία) is the second-largest Greek island in area (3684 square kilometers) and population (213,179 at the 2021 census). It forms most of the regional unit of Euboea (which also includes the island of Skyros and a small area of the Greek mainland), and belongs to the administrative region of Central Greece (Sterea Ellas). For its geographical, environmental and climatic characteristics, see BOROWIEC & SALATA (2018).

The biodiversity of the Euboean ant fauna was previously studied by BOROWIEC & SALATA (2018), who listed 71 species and morphospecies. These were collected exclusively in the central part of the island. Additionally, some additional insights were based on material from the ant collection of the Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle in Geneva, Switzerland and two other

species were recorded from Euboea by LEGAKIS (1984). The island is the type locality for two ant species: *Metalasius myrmidon*, described from the southern part of the island and initially considered its endemic (MEI 1998), but later found in the Peloponnese and Thessaly, and *Temnothorax euboeae*, endemic to the island described based on the worker caste (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2022). Thus, by 2022, 75 ant species were known from the island. However, given the island's size and proximity to mainland Greece, as well as its diverse habitats, it can be expected that up to about 100 species will occur on Euboea.

In this paper, we present a list of ants collected in Euboea from June 16 to 25, 2025. Most of the collecting sites came from the central part of the island, including the alpine parts of Mt. Dirfis, not explored in 2018. There were also sites in the south of the island and in the westernmost parts of Mt. Pyxarias in the high mountain ranges.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The main method, applied at all sites, was direct sampling (hand collecting). Ant nests and individual specimens were collected on the ground, under stones, in dead wood, on tree trunks and twigs. On the banks of roads and forests, ants were brushed off to the entomological umbrella. A litter reducer was used to collect ants found in leaf litter. On the rocks, the ants' nests were searched in rock crevices and using a chisel to obtain a full nest sample. All specimens were collected by L. Borowiec and D. Zięcina and preserved in absolute and 75% ethanol. The list of collecting sites is arranged chronologically, and the list of collected species is arranged alphabetically. General distribution is defined after BOROWIEC (2014) and AntMaps resources (antmaps.org). Distribution in Greek provinces is based on recently published publications on ants of Greece (summarized in BOROWIEC & SALATA 2022, 2025) and unpublished data from the Database and Collection of Greek Ants (DCGA) preserved at the University of Wrocław. Geographical coordinates are given in decimal degrees N/E. The locality codes refer to the position in the coding system used in the DCGA preserved at the University of Wrocław. Material of the most interesting species, prepared or in alcohol, is deposited in the Department of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Taxonomy, Myrmecological Lab, University of Wrocław, Poland.

LIST OF LOCALITIES

(the location of collecting sites is visible on the map in Fig. 1)

1. EUB25_493 – Mt. Olimbos, Ag. Anna chapel, 516 m, 38.45529 / 23.82185, 16 VI 2025, area around chapel.
2. EUB25_494 – Mt. Olimbos loc. 1, 565 m, 38.45843 / 23.82538, 16 VI 2025, phrygana in dry stream valley.
3. EUB25_495 – Mt. Olimbos loc. 2, 578 m, 38.46167 / 23.82888, 16 VI 2025, luminous pine forest.
4. EUB25_496 – Mt. Olimbos loc. 3, 604 m, 38.46559 / 23.82445, 16 VI 2025, luminous pine forest.
5. EUB25_497 – Mt. Olimbos loc. 4, 648 m, 38.45669 / 23.83156, 16 VI 2025, young pine forest with phrygana (Fig. 2).
6. EUB25_498 – 2.3 km NW of Gerontas, 352 m, 38.47107 / 23.80387, 16 VI 2025, water source with large pine trees.
7. EUB25_499 – 2.4 km W of Pournos, 114 m, 38.51709 / 23.75195, 16 VI 2025, pine forest.
8. EUB25_500 – E of Amfithea, 199 m, 38.552 / 23.79544, 16 VI 2025, dry stream bed with herbs on the banks.

9. EUB25_501 – 700 m NE of Seta, 690 m, 38.53747 / 23.9278, 17 VI 2025, dry stream bed with plane and fir trees.
10. EUB25_502 – Ampoudiotissa chapel, 869 m, 38.55941 / 23.9331, 17 VI 2025, dry stream bed with plane trees, and mountain pasture.
11. EUB25_503 – Xerovouni loc. 1, 948 m, 38.57378 / 23.93619, 17 VI 2025, forest glade with ferns.
12. EUB25_504 – Xerovouni loc. 2, 1030 m, 38.57874 / 23.94098, 17 VI 2025, fir forest.
13. EUB25_505 – Xerovouni loc. 3, 1022 m, 38.58738 / 23.9363, 17 VI 2025, stream valley in fir forest.
14. EUB25_506 – Xerovouni loc. 4, 1146 m, 38.59648 / 23.92529, 17 VI 2025, alpine area with rocks (Fig. 3).
15. EUB25_507 – Xerovouni loc. 5, 1105 m, 38.58594 / 23.92591, 17 VI 2025, alpine area with rocks and sparse fir trees (Figs 4 and 5).
16. EUB25_507a – Xerovouni loc. 5, 1105 m, 38.58594 / 23.92591, 21 VI 2025, alpine area with rocks and sparse fir trees.
17. EUB25_508 – Kotillea Mts, 500 m N of Manikia, 437 m, 38.55288 / 23.98917, 18 VI 2025, stream valley with plane trees.
18. EUB25_509 – Kotillea Mts, Prof. Ilias chapel, 495 m, 38.55387 / 23.98872, 18 VI 2025, phrygana with *Quercus coccifera*.
19. EUB25_510 – Kotillea Mts, 800 m NW of Manikia, 550 m, 38.55376 / 23.98356, 18 VI 2025, phrygana with *Quercus coccifera*.
20. EUB25_511 – Neochori, 64 m, 38,54156 / 24,04551, 18 VI 2025, river valley with plane trees.
21. EUB25_512 – Dendra, 238 m, 38.62652 / 24.05399, 18 VI 2025, roadsides with plane trees.
22. EUB25_513 – Vitala, 263 m, 38.63472 / 24.06007, 18 VI 2025, stream valley with plane trees.
23. EUB25_514 – 2.6 km W of Vitala, 482 m, 38.63706 / 24.0278, 18 VI 2025, under large oak in mountain pasture.
24. EUB25_515 – Itamos, 682 m, 38.65482 / 24.00168, 18 VI 2025, fir forest.
25. EUB25_516 – rd. to Rouklia loc. 1, 316 m, 38.09281 / 24.42136, 19 VI 2025, stream valley with shale rocks, and plane and oak trees.
26. EUB25_517 – rd. to Rouklia loc. 2, 341 m, 38.08649 / 24.42159, 19 VI 2025, shale rocks in deciduous forest.
27. EUB25_518 – 1.1 km E of Chania, 207 m, 38.07968 / 24.36858, 19 VI 2025, group of large oak trees in a pasture.
28. EUB25_519 – Distos, 18 m, 38.3689 / 24.1392, 19 VI 2025, farmlands on the outskirts of the salt lake.
29. EUB25_520 – Mt. Dirfis loc. 1, 1108 m, 38.611 / 23.86043, 20 VI 2025, fir forest with limestone rocks.
30. EUB25_521 – Mt. Dirfis loc. 2, 1101 m, 38.61801 / 23.85336, 20 VI 2025, alpine pasture with limestone rocks (Fig. 6).
31. EUB25_522 – Mt. Dirfis loc. 3, 1138 m, 38.61341 / 23.8598, 20 VI 2025, fir forest with limestone rocks.

32. EUB25_523 – Xerovouni loc. 6, 1036 m, 38.58265 / 23.93003, 21 VI 2025, fir forest with limestone rocks.
33. EUB25_524 – Xerovouni loc. 7, 822 m, 38.56412 / 23.93097, 21 VI 2025, young fir forest with limestone rocks.
34. EUB25_525 – 1.8 km NW of Kato Seta, 756 m, 38.55206 / 23.92564, 21 VI 2025, stream valley with plane trees inside fir forest (Fig. 7).
35. EUB25_526 – Kato Seta, 670 m, 38.54004 / 23.93169, 21 VI 2025, stream valley with plane trees.
36. EUB25_527 – Mt. Dirfis loc. 4, 928 m, 38.63711 / 23.81406, 22 VI 2025, fir forest.
37. EUB25_528 – Mt. Dirfis loc. 5, 823 m, 38.6385 / 23.80364, 22 VI 2025, rocks on roadsides.
38. EUB25_529 – Mt. Dirfis loc. 6, 522 m, 38.63291 / 23.78687, 22 VI 2025, pine forest.
39. EUB25_530 – Mt. Dirfis loc. 7, 262 m, 38.61823 / 23.78111, 22 VI 2025, pine forest.
40. EUB25_531 – Mt. Dirfis loc. 8, 262 m, 38.61626 / 23.78288, 22 VI 2025, stream valley with plane trees.
41. EUB25_532 – Mt. Dirfis, Agali Gorge, 282 m, 38.61029 / 23.79668, 22 VI 2025, stream valley with plane trees.
42. EUB25_533 – 2.4 km SE of Amfithea, 206 m, 38.5294 / 23.76812, 22 VI 2025, pine forest.
43. EUB25_534 – 1.6 km S of Stropones, 575 m, 38.60369 / 23.88609, 23 VI 2025, stream valley with plane trees and roadsides with Rosaceae bushes.
44. EUB25_535 – 2.5 km S of Stropones, 730 m, 38.5962 / 23.88555, 23 VI 2025, mixed fir and sweet chestnut forest.
45. EUB25_536 – 2.3 km SW of Stropones, 862 m, 38.59955 / 23.87797, 23 VI 2025, mixed fir and sweet chestnut forest.
46. EUB25_537 – 2.7 km SW of Stropones, 933 m, 38.59748 / 23.87319, 23 VI 2025, stream valley with plane trees inside fir forest.
47. EUB25_538 – 2.4 km SW of Stropones, 917 m, 38.60067 / 23.87253, 23 VI 2025, fir forest.
48. EUB25_539 – 2.2 km SW of Stropones, 885 m, 38.60342 / 23.87209, 23 VI 2025, fir forest.
49. EUB25_540 – 4.3 km SW of Ag. Sofia, 913 m, 38.67145 / 23.68048, 24 VI 2025, luminous fir forest with limestone rocks.
50. EUB25_541 – 4.6 km SW of Ag. Sofia, 885 m, 38.66789 / 23.67607, 24 VI 2025, fir forest with limestone rocks.
51. EUB25_542 – 5 km SW of Ag. Sofia, 863 m, 38.66252 / 23.67754, 24 VI 2025, fir forest with limestone rocks.
52. EUB25_543 – 5.7 km SW of Ag. Sofia, 820 m, 38.65907 / 23.66903, 24 VI 2025, fir forest with limestone rocks.
53. EUB25_544 – 3.3 km N of Kondodestopi, 719 m, 38.65458 / 23.64291, 24 VI 2025, mixed forest.
54. EUB25_545 – 3.3 km S of Koutourla, 830 m, 38.61251 / 23.91999, 25 VI 2025, fir forest.
55. EUB25_546 – 4.5 km S of Koutourla, 816 m, 38.60247 / 23.9154, 25 VI 2025, stream valley with plane trees.

56. EUB25_547 – 2.7 km S of Stropones, 832 m, 38.59324 / 23.88708, 25 VI 2025, fir forest (Fig. 8).
57. EUB25_548 – 2.8 km S of Stropones, 900 m, 38.59441 / 23.87879, 25 VI 2025, mixed fir and sweet chestnut forest.
58. EUB25_549 – Hotel Evia Riviera Resort, 5-13 m, 38.38751 / 23.93236, 16-25 VI 2025, hotel area.

LIST OF COLLECTED SPECIES

1. *Aphaenogaster balcanica* (EMERY, 1898)

Localities: 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 35, 42, 58.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species, in Greece recorded from all provinces except Crete.

2. *Aphaenogaster epirotes* (EMERY, 1895)

Localities: 4, 8, 25, 53.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species, recorded from all mainland provinces, the Cyclades, the East Aegean Islands, and the Ionian Islands.

3. *Aphaenogaster subterranea* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 8, 9, 10, 13, 21, 22, 34, 35, 43, 44, 45, 46, 54, 55.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species, in Greece recorded from all provinces except Crete. In our previous paper on ants of Euboea (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018), it was recorded under two names: *Aphaenogaster subterranea* (LATREILLE, 1798) and *Aphaenogaster* cf. *subterranea* sp. 1 due to the occurrence of two distinct morphotypes separated by habitat preferences. The most recent revision of this complex (ZIĘCINA *et al.* 2024) showed that both forms represent only two ecotypes of a single species.

4. *Aphaenogaster tristis* BOROWIEC, MENCHETTI, SALATA, VILA & ZIĘCINA, 2024

Localities: 15, 16, 22, 29, 31, 32, 36, 40, 49, 50, 51, 56, 57.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare species, recently described from Cyclades, the Ionian Islands, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly. A nest samples containing a well preserved gynes were collected at sites 31, 50, 51. These are the first finds of well-preserved gyne caste in *Aphaenogaster tristis*. Its description will appear in the currently prepared third volume of the monograph on the ants of Greece. In our previous paper on ants of Euboea (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018), it was recorded as *Aphaenogaster* cf. *subterranea* sp. 2.

5. *Bothriomyrmex communista* SANTSCHI, 1919

Localities: 11, 16, 30.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species, in Greece recorded from all provinces except Crete.

6. *Camponotus aethiops* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 1, 4, 5, 25, 29, 32, 36, 37.

Distribution in Greece: It is a very common species, in Greece recorded from all provinces.

7. *Camponotus dalmaticus* (NYLANDER, 1849)

Localities: 8, 19, 22, 24, 27, 39, 40, 43, 56.

Distribution in Greece: It is a northern and western species, known from all mainland provinces, the East Aegean Islands, and the Ionian Islands.

8. *Camponotus fallax* (NYLANDER, 1856)

Localities: 12, 31, 45, 56.

Distribution in Greece: It is an uncommon species on the mainland and a rare species on the islands, recorded from the East Aegean Islands, the Ionian Islands, and the Dodecanese.

9. *Camponotus ionius* EMERY, 1920

Localities: 6, 17, 18, 19, 38, 39, 40, 41, 58.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species known from all Greek provinces except Crete.

10. *Camponotus kiesenwetteri* (ROGER, 1859)

Localities: 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 17, 42.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in central and southern Greece and uncommon in northern Greece; it is still unknown from Epirus.

11. *Camponotus laconicus* EMERY, 1920

Localities: 1, 4, 7.

Distribution in Greece: It is an uncommon species recorded only from the Peloponnese and the Euboea Island.

12. *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER, 1792)

Localities: 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 9, 10, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 25, 26, 27, 35, 38, 39, 41, 49, 58.

Distribution in Greece: It is one of the most common Greek *Camponotus* species recorded from all regions.

13. *Camponotus ligniperda* (LATREILLE, 1802)

Localities: 46.

Distribution in Greece: It is an uncommon species known from the mountains of all mainland provinces (except Thrace) and from the Ionian Islands.

14. *Camponotus oertzeni* FOREL, 1889

Localities: 2, 3, 9, 11, 14, 15, 16, 29, 31, 36, 47, 48, 51, 52, 53, 55, 57.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common Greek species often misidentified with *Camponotus aethiops*, known from all provinces.

15. *Camponotus piceus* (LEACH, 1825)

Localities: 11, 14, 15, 16, 30, 32, 36, 55.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands, rare in Crete and the East Aegean Islands; records from the Cyclades and the Dodecanese need confirmation.

16. *Camponotus* cf. *piceus*

Localities: 29, 31, 36, 37, 43, 48, 49, 50, 56, 57.

Distribution in Greece: It is an undescribed species closely related to *Camponotus piceus*. Its description, with detailed morphometric data, and a comparison with other black species of the *Camponotus lateralis* complex will be published in a separate paper.

17. *Camponotus vagus* (SCOPOLI, 1763)

Localities: 9, 13, 24, 29, 31, 32, 33, 35, 36, 38, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 56, 57.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands, rare in Crete and the East Aegean Islands.

18. *Cataglyphis hellenica* (FOREL, 1886)

Localities: 1.

Distribution in Greece: It is an uncommon species recorded from the East Aegean Islands, Crete, Cyclades, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, and Sterea Ellas.

19. *Cataglyphis nodus* (BRULLÉ, 1833)

Localities: 1, 4, 5, 7, 18, 20, 23, 24, 25, 26, 28, 29, 38, 40, 41, 53, 58.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species recorded from most of the regions except the Cyclades, and with one doubtful record from Crete.

20. *Chalepoxenus muellerianus* (FINZI, 1922)

Localities: 14, 17.

Distribution in Greece: It is a social parasite in nests of various species of the genus *Temnothorax*, especially of the *T. recedens* group. In Greece, it is recorded from mainland provinces except Thrace, and also from Crete and the Ionian Islands. In Euboea, found in nests of *T. recedens*, and *Temnothorax* cf. *tuborum*_long spined.

21. *Colobopsis truncata* (SPINOLA, 1808)

Localities: 21, 22, 39.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species recorded from all regions.

22. *Crematogaster ionia* (FOREL, 1911)

Localities: 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 23, 25, 26, 27, 34, 35, 36, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 49, 53, 54, 56, 58.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species recorded in southern and eastern Greek provinces, especially on the islands, rare in northern and western provinces. In our previous paper on ants of Euboea (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018), it was recorded under the name *Crematogaster schmidti* MAYR, 1853.

23. *Crematogaster sordidula* (NYLANDER, 1849)

Localities: 18, 39.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species recorded from all Greek provinces.

24. *Dolichoderus quadripunctatus* (LINNAEUS, 1771)

Localities: 21, 22.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species recorded from most regions, except Crete and the Cyclades.

25. *Formica fusca* LINNAEUS, 1758

Localities: 3, 5, 9, 11, 13, 14, 15, 29, 31, 35, 38, 43, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 56.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species on the Greek mainland's mountains and on the islands, known only from Crete and the Ionian Islands.

26. *Formica sanguinea* LATREILLE, 1798

Localities: 11, 12, 14, 56.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare species, known only from high mountain elevations in Epirus, Macedonia, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly, and Thrace.

27. *Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER, 1850)

Localities: 9, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 26, 29, 30, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 44, 45, 47, 48, 50, 51, 54, 55.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in the northern mainland, but uncommon in the southern mainland and on the islands.

28. *Lasius brunneus* (LATREILLE, 1798)
Localities: 9, 13, 43, 54.
Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species in the mountains of the Greek mainland and on the islands, known only from the East Aegean and the Ionian Islands.
29. *Lasius flavus* (FABRICIUS, 1782)
Localities: 9, 13, 29, 31, 45, 49, 51, 54, 56.
Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in the mountains of the Greek mainland and on islands known only from the East Aegean and the Ionian Islands.
30. *Lasius illyricus* ZIMMERMANN, 1935
Localities: 10, 13, 16, 31, 43, 45, 46, 48, 50, 51, 54, 56, 57.
Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland, rare in the islands, but not recorded from the Cyclades.
31. *Lasius lasioides* (EMERY, 1869)
Localities: 1, 3, 4, 17, 25, 27, 37, 52, 53, 58.
Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species known from all provinces.
32. *Lasius neglectus* VAN LOON, BOOMSMA & ANDRASFALVY, 1990
Locality: 26.
Distribution in Greece: It is an uncommon species, recorded from the Cyclades, the Dodecanese, the East Aegean Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Thessaly and Thrace.
33. *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* (MAYR, 1855)
Localities: 1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 17, 18, 23, 35, 41.
Distribution in Greece: This species was recorded from all Greek provinces except the Cyclades, but according to BOROWIEC & SALATA (2022), it is probably a complex of cryptic taxa that requires revision based on morphometric and molecular studies. The populations from Euboea have characters of the typical form known from mainland provinces.
34. *Messor hellenius* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987
Localities: 1, 6.
Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species but known from all Greek provinces. In Euboea, the predominant form has reduced striate sculpture on the head.
35. *Messor ibericus* SANTSCHI, 1931
Localities: 17, 43, 58.
Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species but known from all Greek provinces.
36. *Messor structor* (LATREILLE, 1798)
Localities: 10, 11, 15, 16, 29, 30, 32, 48, 49.
Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in the mountains of all mainland provinces, on the islands known only from the Cyclades.
37. *Messor wasmanni* KRAUSSE, 1910
Localities: 1, 18, 25, 35.
Distribution in Greece: It is a common species recorded from all Greek provinces.
38. *Metalasius myrmidon* (MEI, 1998)
Locality: 25.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare species, described from Euboea then recorded from the Peloponnese and Thessaly.

39. *Myrmecina graminicola* (LATREILLE, 1802)

Localities: 9, 44.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland, rare in the island provinces.

40. *Myrmica pelops* SEIFERT, 2003

Locality: 36.

Distribution in Greece: It is a very rare species endemic to Greece. Recorded from the Peloponnese (locus typicus), Sterea Ellas, and Thessaly.

41. *Myrmica scabrinodis* NYLANDER, 1846

Localities: 12, 13, 15, 16, 29, 31, 45, 46.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland and the Ionian Islands.

42. *Myrmoxenus menozzii* FINZI, 1924

Locality: 49.

Distribution in Greece: It is a social parasite in nests of various species of the genus *Temnothorax*, recorded from the East Aegean Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly. In Euboea, collected from the nest of *Temnothorax helenae*.

43. *Nylanderia jaegerskioeldi* (MAYR, 1904)

Locality: 58.

Distribution in Greece: It is an invasive species collected in anthropogenic urban habitats from Crete, the Dodecanese, the East Aegean Islands, the Ionian Islands, the Peloponnese and Sterea Ellas.

44. *Pheidole* cf. *pallidula* complex

Localities: 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 11, 14, 15, 17, 18, 19, 20, 23, 24, 25, 27, 29, 30, 31, 32, 35, 36, 38, 39, 40, 41, 48, 49, 51, 52, 53, 57, 58.

Distribution in Greece: The Mediterranean populations of the taxon *Pheidole pallidula* (NYLANDER, 1849) have recently been divided into four species, three of which have been recorded in Greece (SEIFERT 2016). However, this point of view remains under discussion owing to the substantial local variability of this common Mediterranean ant. The small number of major workers from Euboea precludes precise identification, so we report them as *Pheidole* cf. *pallidula* complex. In the material examined by B. Seifert there were no specimens from Euboea, and from the zoogeographic point of view on this island *P. balcanica* SEIFERT and *P. koshewnikovi* RUZSKY may occur.

45. *Plagiolepis perperamus* SALATA, BOROWIEC & RADCHENKO, 2018

Localities: 4, 8, 10, 25, 32, 33, 37.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species known from all Greek provinces. In the previous paper on ants from Euboea (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018), it was noted under the name *Plagiolepis pallescens* sensu RADCHENKO.

46. *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 14, 15, 16, 17, 21, 24, 25, 26, 28, 30, 32, 34, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 45, 47, 48, 49, 55, 56, 57, 58.

Distribution in Greece: It is a very common species recorded from all Greek provinces.

47. *Plagiolepis taurica* SANTSCHI, 1920

Localities: 5, 11, 21, 29, 53, 58.

Distribution in Greece: According to KIRSCHNER *et al.* (2023) in the western part of mainland Greece occurs *Plagiolepis taurica* SANTSCHI, 1920. Re-examination of our materials of this group from Greece and Cyprus indicates the presence of two species in Greece, *P. taurica* and *P. pallescens* FOREL, 1889. The latter is probably more widely distributed in the east. Confirmed samples of *P. taurica* we have from all mainland provinces; populations from Euboea also belong to this species.

48. *Ponera coarctata* (LATREILLE, 1802)

Locality: 9.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland, the East Aegean Islands, and the Ionian Islands.

49. *Solenopsis juliae* (ARAKELIAN, 1991)

Localities: 2, 3, 4, 9, 14, 18, 27, 30, 35, 39, 40, 41, 50.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species known from all provinces except Crete. In the previous paper on ants from Euboea (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018) noted under name *Solenopsis wolfi*.

50. *Tapinoma glabrellum* NYLANDER, 1849

Localities: 3, 8, 11, 12, 14, 15, 16, 24, 30, 32, 35, 36, 40, 52, 54.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species recorded from all Greek provinces. In the previous paper on ants from Euboea (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018) noted under name *Tapinoma erraticum*.

51. *Temnothorax affinis* (MAYR, 1855)

Locality: 48.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare species recorded from the Cyclades, the East Aegean Islands, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace.

52. *Temnothorax angustifrons* CSŐSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ, 2015

Locality: 38.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in the East Aegean Islands, rare in Thrace, record from Euboea is the only from Sterea Ellas and the westernmost for this species.

53. *Temnothorax balcanicus* (SANTSCHI, 1909)

Localities: 14, 16, 29, 30, 37.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species recorded from all provinces except the Ionian Islands. In all previous papers, this taxon was recorded from Greece and from Euboea as *Temnothorax semiruber* (ANDRÉ, 1881), but the recent revision of the *Temnothorax rottenbergii* species group (CSŐSZ *et al.* 2025) showed that *T. balcanicus* and *T. semiruber* are closely related but distinct species and in the Euboea occurs only *Temnothorax balcanicus*.

54. *Temnothorax brackoi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2019

Localities: 21, 22, 43.

Distribution in Greece: It is a recently described species known from all mainland provinces but common only in the western part of this area. At site 43, an initial nest containing a queen (+ seven workers) was found in a dry branch of a *Rubus* sp. shrub. This is

the first find of this caste in *Temnothorax brackoi*. Its description will appear in the currently prepared third volume of the monograph on the ants of Greece. In the previous paper on ants from Euboea (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018) recorded under the name *Temnothorax cf. aveli*.

55. *Temnothorax bulgaricus* (FOREL, 1892)

Localities: 1, 7, 8, 20, 21, 23, 40.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species recorded from all Greek provinces except Crete.

56. *Temnothorax cf. exilis*

Locality: 3.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species known from most of Greek provinces except Crete and the Dodecanese. The *Temnothorax exilis* group is under revision and probably most Greek populations of this complex, including populations from the Euboea, will be named *Temnothorax darii* (FOREL, 1911) - currently junior synonym of *T. exilis*.

57. *Temnothorax euboeae* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2022

Localities: 14, 15, 16.

Distribution in Greece: It is a recently described species, endemic to Euboea. Due to the clearly distinct characters of this species from other species in the *Temnothorax anodontoides* group, it was described despite the fact that only one specimen of a worker was available (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2022). The currently collected material includes two nest samples with gynes, two nest samples without gynes, and two samples from workers foraging on limestone rocks. This abundant material confirms the distinctness of this species. First description of the gyne of this species will appear in the currently prepared third volume of the monograph on the ants of Greece.

58. *Temnothorax flavicornis* (EMERY, 1870)

Locality: 58.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare species, recorded from the East Aegean Islands, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly.

59. *Temnothorax graecus* (FOREL, 1911)

Localities: 1, 7, 8, 17, 18, 20, 21, 27, 39, 41.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species, with terra typica in the Achaia unit of the Peloponnese, recorded there, as well as from the Cyclades, the Dodecanese, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly, and Thrace.

60. *Temnothorax helenae* CSÖSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ, 2015

Localities: 2, 3, 4, 5, 9, 12, 15, 16, 19, 20, 21, 22, 24, 27, 29, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 43, 44, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 54, 55, 56.

Distribution in Greece: It is a recently described species, endemic to Greece, recorded from most mainland provinces except Epirus and from Crete and the Cyclades.

61. *Temnothorax kemali* (SANTSCHI, 1934)

Locality: 7.

Distribution in Greece: Recent revision of the *Temnothorax kemali* species group (ZIECINA *et al.* 2025) showed that in Greece occur only one species from this group conspecific with the true *T. kemali* described from Türkiye. It is common in the East Aegean Islands and the Dodecanese, moderately common in eastern parts of Sterea Ellas and Thessaly, and rare in the

Ionian Islands and the Peloponnese. In the previous paper on ants from Euboea (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018), the species was noted as *Temnothorax* cf. *kemali*.

62. *Temnothorax lichtensteini* (BONDROIT, 1918)

Localities: 2, 6, 21, 34, 43, 55, 57.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in northern and central Greece, recorded from the East Aegean Islands, Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace.

63. *Temnothorax messiniaensis* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2019

Locality: 43.

Distribution in Greece: It is a recently described species endemic to Greece, common in the Ionian Islands and the Peloponnese and with few records from Sterea Ellas and Thessaly.

64. *Temnothorax morea* CSŐSZ, SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2018

Locality: 4.

Distribution in Greece: It is a recently described species known from Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly.

65. *Temnothorax recedens* (NYLANDER, 1856)

Localities: 2, 3, 5, 8, 17, 19, 20, 23, 25, 26, 27, 38, 39., 40, 41, 56, 58.

Distribution in Greece: It is the commonest Greek member of the genus *Temnothorax* known from all provinces.

66. *Temnothorax strymonensis* CSŐSZ, SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2018

Localities: 3, 38, 39, 41.

Distribution in Greece: It is a recently described species known from the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Thessaly, and Thrace.

67. *Temnothorax subtilis* CSŐSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ, 2015

Localities: 22, 31, 32, 36, 41, 45, 46, 53, 55.

Distribution in Greece: It is a recently described species known from Crete, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Thessaly, and Thrace.

68. *Temnothorax triangularis* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2019

Localities: 10, 12, 13, 15, 16, 29, 32, 33, 34, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 50, 54, 56, 57.

Distribution in Greece: It is a recently described species, endemic to Euboea. In the previous paper on ants from Euboea (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018) noted under name *Temnothorax* cf. *nylanderi*.

69. *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum*_long spine

Localities: 14, 16, 30, 31.

Distribution in Greece: Greek species of the *Temnothorax tuberum* complex require revision. Populations from Greece differ from populations from Central Europe and perhaps represent other cryptic species. *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum*_long spine is characterized by extremely long propodeal spines and is common in all mountain regions of mainland Greece and the Ionian Islands.

70. *Temnothorax turcicus* (SANTSCHI, 1934)

Localities: 7, 8, 35, 39, 43, 47.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common arboreal species known from all

mainland provinces and the East Aegean Islands. In the previous paper on ants from Euboea (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018) noted under name *Temnothorax* cf. *turcicus*.

71. *Temnothorax unifasciatus* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 9, 10, 12, 14, 15, 16, 24, 29, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 43, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 55, 56.

Distribution in Greece: The Greek species of the *Temnothorax unifasciatus* complex require revision. Some populations from Greece differ slightly from those in Central Europe and may represent a few cryptic species. The samples noted in this paper appear to be typical *T. unifasciatus*.

72. *Tetramorium caespitum* (LINNAEUS, 1758)

Localities: 14, 16, 31, 32, 51.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species recorded from the mountains of Epirus, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Thessaly and Thrace.

73. *Tetramorium diomedea* EMERY, 1908

Localities: 1, 4.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species recorded from all Greek provinces except Sterea Ellas.

74. *Tetramorium hippocratis* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987

Locality: 19.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare species, although recorded from most of the Greek provinces except Epirus and the Ionian Islands.

75. *Tetramorium immigrans* SANTSCHI, 1927

Locality: 58.

Distribution in Greece: It is a cosmopolitan species known from all Greek provinces except Epirus reported mainly from anthropogenic habitats, in urban areas and tourist resorts.

76. *Tetramorium impurum* (FÖRSTER, 1850)

Localities: 14, 29, 30, 50, 53.

Distribution in Greece: It is a mountain species, recorded from all mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands.

77. *Tetramorium kephalosi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2017

Localities: 10, 25, 31, 52, 53, 58.

Distribution in Greece: It is the most common Greek member of the genus *Tetramorium*, recorded from all provinces.

78. *Tetramorium* cf. *punicum* complex

Localities: 30, 49.

Distribution in Greece: It is probably an undescribed species of uncertain taxonomic position. Although it was collected in seven Greek provinces, primarily in the south of the country, no sexual forms of this taxon have been found to date, and we are unable to even determine which species group it belongs to. At first glance it is similar to the Mediterranean species close to *Tetramorium punicum* (SMITH, 1861).

UPDATED CHECKLIST OF ANT SPECIES KNOWN FROM EUBOEA ISLAND

1. *Aphaenogaster balcanica* (EMERY, 1898)
2. *Aphaenogaster epirotes* (EMERY, 1895)
3. *Aphaenogaster subterranea* (LATREILLE, 1798)
4. *Aphaenogaster tristis* ZIĘCINA *et al.*, 2024
5. *Bothriomyrmex communista* SANTSCHI, 1919
6. *Camponotus aethiops* (LATREILLE, 1798)
7. *Camponotus dalmaticus* (NYLANDER, 1849)
8. *Camponotus fallax* (NYLANDER, 1856)
9. *Camponotus gestroi* EMERY, 1878
10. *Camponotus ionius* EMERY, 1920
11. *Camponotus kiesenwetteri* (ROGER, 1859)
12. *Camponotus laconicus* EMERY, 1920
13. *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER, 1792)
14. *Camponotus ligniperda* (LATREILLE, 1802)
15. *Camponotus oertzeni* FOREL, 1889
16. *Camponotus piceus* (LEACH, 1825)
17. *Camponotus* cf. *piceus*
18. *Camponotus vagus* (SCOPOLI, 1763)
19. *Carebara oertzeni* FOREL, 1886
20. *Cataglyphis hellenica* (FOREL, 1886)
21. *Cataglyphis nodus* (BRULLÉ, 1833)
22. *Chalepoxenus muellerianus* (FINZI, 1922)
23. *Colobopsis truncata* (SPINOLA, 1808)
24. *Crematogaster ionia* (FOREL, 1911)
25. *Crematogaster lorteti* FOREL, 1910
26. *Crematogaster sordidula* (NYLANDER, 1849)
27. *Dolichoderus quadripunctatus* (LINNAEUS, 1771)
28. *Formica fusca* LINNAEUS, 1758
29. *Formica gagates* LATREILLE, 1798
30. *Formica sanguinea* LATREILLE, 1798
31. *Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER, 1850)
32. *Lasius bombycinus* SEIFERT & GALKOWSKI, 2026
33. *Lasius brunneus* (LATREILLE, 1798)
34. *Lasius distinguendus* (EMERY, 1916) or *L. balcanicus* SEIFERT, 1988
35. *Lasius flavus* (FABRICIUS, 1782)
36. *Lasius illyricus* ZIMMERMANN, 1935
37. *Lasius lasioides* (EMERY, 1869)

38. *Lasius neglectus* VAN LOON, BOOMSMA & ANDRASFALVY, 1990
39. *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* (MAYR, 1855)
40. *Messor hellenius* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987
41. *Messor ibericus* SANTSCHI, 1931
42. *Messor structor* (LATREILLE, 1798)
43. *Messor wasmanni* KRAUSSE, 1910
44. *Metalasius myrmidon* (MEI, 1998)
45. *Myrmecina graminicola* (LATREILLE, 1802)
46. *Myrmica pelops* SEIFERT, 2003
47. *Myrmica scabrinodis* NYLANDER, 1846
48. *Myrmoxenus menozzii* FINZI, 1924
49. *Myrmoxenus ravouxi* (ANDRÉ, 1896)
50. *Nylanderia jaegerskioeldi* (MAYR, 1904)
51. *Pheidole* cf. *pallidula* complex
52. *Plagiolepis perperamus* SALATA, BOROWIEC & RADCHENKO, 2018
53. *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (LATREILLE, 1798)
54. *Plagiolepis taurica* SANTSCHI, 1920
55. *Ponera coarctata* (LATREILLE, 1802)
56. *Prenolepis nitens* (MAYR, 1853)
57. *Proceratium numidicum* SANTSCHI, 1912
58. *Solenopsis juliae* (ARAKELIAN, 1991)
59. *Stenamamma debile* (FÖRSTER, 1850)
60. *Tapinoma glabrellum* NYLANDER, 1849
61. *Temnothorax affinis* (MAYR, 1855)
62. *Temnothorax angustifrons* CSŐSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ, 2015
63. *Temnothorax balcanicus* (SANTSCHI, 1909)
64. *Temnothorax brackoi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2019
65. *Temnothorax bulgaricus* (FOREL, 1892)
66. *Temnothorax crasecundus* SEIFERT & CSŐSZ, 2015
67. *Temnothorax* cf. *exilis* (EMERY, 1869)
68. *Temnothorax euboeae* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2022
69. *Temnothorax flavicornis* (EMERY, 1870)
70. *Temnothorax graecus* (FOREL, 1911)
71. *Temnothorax helenae* CSŐSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ, 2015
72. *Temnothorax kemali* (SANTSCHI, 1934)
73. *Temnothorax lichtensteini* (BONDROIT, 1918)
74. *Temnothorax messiniaensis* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2019
75. *Temnothorax morea* CSŐSZ, SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2018
76. *Temnothorax parvulus* (SCHENCK, 1852)

77. *Temnothorax recedens* (NYLANDER, 1856)
78. *Temnothorax strymonensis* CSÓSZ, SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2018
79. *Temnothorax subtilis* CSÓSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ, 2015
80. *Temnothorax triangularis* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2019
81. *Temnothorax* cf. *tubерum*_long spine
82. *Temnothorax turcicus* (SANTSCHI, 1934)
83. *Temnothorax unifasciatus* (LATREILLE, 1798)
84. *Tetramorium caespitum* (LINNAEUS, 1758)
85. *Tetramorium chefketi* FOREL, 1911
86. *Tetramorium diomedaeum* EMERY, 1908
87. *Tetramorium flavidulum* EMERY, 1924
88. *Tetramorium hippocratis* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987
89. *Tetramorium immigrans* SANTSCHI, 1927
90. *Tetramorium impurum* (FÖRSTER, 1850)
91. *Tetramorium kephalosi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2017
92. *Tetramorium* cf. *punicum* complex

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Fig. 1. Map of collecting sites (black circles).

Fig. 2. Locality 5: Mt. Olimbos, young pine forest with phrygana, habitat for thermophilic species such as *Aphaenogaster balcanica*, *Camponotus kiesewetteri*, *Cataglyphis nodus*, *Crematogaster ionia*, *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* and *Plagiolepis taurica*.

Fig. 3. Locality 14: Alpine pastures in the Xerovouni area, habitat for endemic *Temnothorax euboae*, still undescribed *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum*_long spined, and *Temnothorax balcanicus*.

Fig. 4. Locality 15: A rock in the Xerovouni area where a nest of the endemic *Temnothorax euboae* was found.

Figs. 5–6. Fig. 5 (above). Locality 15: Mountain pasture with rocks and sparse fir trees in the Xerovouni area, habitat for endemic *Temnothorax euboae*, *T. helenae*, endemic *T. triangularis* and *T. unifasciatus*; Fig. 6 (below). Locality 30: Alpine part of Mt. Dirfis, habitat for still undescribed *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum*_long spined, a typical alpine species in the mountains of Greece.

Fig. 7. Locality 34: Stream valley with plane trees inside fir forest near Kato Seta, typical habitat for endemic *Temnothorax triangularis*.

Fig. 8. Locality 56: Old fir forest, habitat for the Greek endemic *Aphaenogaster tristis* and an undescribed species endemic to Euboea *Camponotus* cf. *piceus*.

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